

Ketosis (Acetonemia) in dairy cows

Sonam Bhatt^{1*}, Anil kumar², Bhoomika Sirsant³, Pankaj Kumar⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary medicine, Bihar Veterinary College, BASU, Patna

²Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Clinical Complex, Bihar Veterinary College, BASU, Patna

³Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Public Health, Bihar Veterinary College, BASU, Patna

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Parasitology, Bihar Veterinary College, BASU, Patna

Introduction

Ketosis is one of the most important and common metabolic disorder of dairy cows. It is also known as acetonemia and is characterized by high levels of circulating ketone bodies, which frequently result in productivity and reproductive losses, as well as death or early culling. There is an increase in ketone bodies in the blood of dairy cows to the point where they release into the urine and (or) milk. In dairy cows, ketosis is a lactation disorder characterized by excessive milk production and a negative energy balance. It is essentially an energy deficit manifested as a drop in blood glucose during times when the animal's energy demand is high, such as late pregnancy and early lactation. If the animal cannot or does not eat enough to meet demand, it will use other resources for energy, most notably body fat, resulting in the production of large amounts of chemical by products known as ketone bodies.

Etiology

It is a multifactorial disease associated with intense milk production and negative energy balance in dairy cattle. Ketosis occurs in the early postpartum period in dairy cows where there is an increase in demand for glucose and insufficient propionate production.

Epidemiology

It occurs worldwide and is common in ruminants. It mainly occurs during the transition period of the cow. Risk factors associated for development of ketosis include breed, lactation, presence of disease condition that causes anorexia in cows, BCS at calving, dry period length and other managemental factors.

Pathogenesis

Ketosis in a high producing dairy cow is related to a negative energy balance in the first few

weeks of lactation. Negative energy balance leads to adipose mobilization and a high glucose demand. Adipose mobilization is accompanied by high serum concentrations of non-esterified fatty acids (NEFAs). Further, NEFAs initiate the production of ketone bodies by the liver. The ketone body circulates in the blood, found in the urine and milk. Thus, the ketosis is clinically characterized by low concentrations of glucose, high serum concentrations of NEFAs and ketone bodies.

(Source: Tadesse et al., 2019)

Classification of ketosis

- Primary underfeeding- Also known as starvation ketosis and occurs when feed quality is inadequate.
- Secondary underfeeding ketosis – Occurs when there is inadequate feed intake due to concurrent disease condition.
- Ketogenic or alimentary ketosis – Occurs from feeds high in ketogenic material.
- Ketosis due to a specific nutritional deficiency – Nutrients like Cobalt and possibly phosphorus deficiency has been suspected as causes.
- Spontaneous ketosis - Where causes are not able to be established.

Clinical signs

Clinical signs include wasting and nervous form. Wasting form is the most common form which is manifested with a gradual but moderate decrease in appetite. Decrease in milk yield and body weight

is lost rapidly. There is woody appearance of affected animal due to wasting and loss of cutaneous elasticity. In the later stage, animal appear as hang dog and is disinclination to move. Odor of ketones is detectable in breath and often in the milk.

Nervous form of ketosis includes circling, straddling and crossing of the legs, head pushing, apparent blindness, Depraved appetite and chewing movements with salivation.

Diagnosis

An accurate diagnosis of ketosis is extremely important for the effective treatment. Various complications associated with ketosis are metritis, retained placenta, nephritis, and other abnormalities. In such cases, it is difficult to determine whether the ketosis is primary or secondary. Treatment generally used for primary ketosis would not be expected to be particularly effective in complicated cases.

Clinical form of ketosis is diagnosed by the following basis

- History of presence of early lactation and last stage of pregnancy.
- Based on the clinical signs like decreased milk production, reduced feed intake, smell of ketone bodies in milk and urine.
- **Hypoglycemia, ketonemia and ketonuria** are characteristic of the disease.
- **Glucose level:** Blood glucose level are reduced from the normal of approximately 50mg/dl to 20-40 mg/dl.
- **Blood ketones:** Most commonly, plasma or serum beta hydroxybutyrate (BHBA) measured in SI units is used for the analysis of ketonemia. BHBA is the predominant circulating ketone body. Normal cows have plasma BHBA concentrations less than 1000 μ mol/L, cows with subclinical ketosis have concentrations greater than 1400 μ mol/L and cows with clinical ketosis have concentrations on excess of 2500 μ mol/L.
- **Milk and urine cow side tests:** Dipstick urine and milk tests measure the ketone body concentrations, give immediate results and can be used frequently as necessary.

Differential Diagnosis

Wasting form of the ketosis may be differentiated from the following:

- Abomasal displacement
- Traumatic reticulitis
- Primary indigestion
- Cystitis and pyelonephritis
- Diabetes mellitus

Nervous form of the ketosis may be differentiated from the following:

- Rabies
- Hypomagnesemia
- Bovine spongiform encephalopathy

Treatment

Treatment of ketosis is aimed to relieve the need for glucose formation from tissues and reducing serum ketone body concentrations.

Replacement therapy

- Glucose (dextrose): IV injection of 500ml of a 50 % solution of glucose results in hyperglycemia, increased insulin and decreased glucagon secretion and reduced plasma concentration of non-esterified fatty acids.
- Propylene glycol: It acts as a glucose precursor and is administered as a drench. Dose of 225g twice daily for 2 days followed by 110g daily for 2 days is used for treating ketosis in cattle.

Hormonal therapy

- Glucocorticoids: IV glucose with corticosteroids may be used for the treatment of ketosis.
- Insulin: It suppresses both adipose mobilization and ketogenesis. Dose of protamine zinc insulin is 200-300 IU, SC.

Prevention and control

- It can be prevented by nutritional and cow management.
- Provide balance ration to the milking and dry cows.
- Use of energy supplements like propylene glycol, propionic acid and its salts.
- Regular monitoring of herd for subclinical ketosis and estimation of blood glucose concentration of cows in their second week of lactation.

Conclusion

Ketosis is one of the most essential diseases of high yielding cows. It causes severe economic loss to the dairy farmers and dairy industry. Losses in ketosis are in terms of reduced milk production, treatment cost and impaired reproductive performances. Therefore, prevention and control measures should always be followed in a herd.

